

Webinar - Putting users first: how can we co-create environmental data services that address real needs

Authors:

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

The webinar focused on the importance of co-creating environmental data services by involving users directly in their development. This approach ensures that the services are relevant, usable, and effective in addressing environmental challenges.

Why Co-Creation Matters - Poppy Townsend

- **User-Centric Design:** Emphasises the shift towards designing services with user feedback, aiming to increase user satisfaction and service impact.
- **Funders' Requirements:** Highlighted the necessity to adapt to funders' expectations by incorporating user feedback into service design, maintenance, and sharing.

Current Progress and Activities - Poppy Townsend

- **BOOST-EDS Project:** Part of the DSIT RDCP funding project, specifically focusing on Work Package 5 (WP5) which deals with the co-creation of user-focused services.
- **March 2024 Workshop:** Conducted a two-hour workshop with 24 technical experts, identifying four key themes: **ineffective sharing of learnings, engagement challenges, lack of resources, and difficulties in user engagement.**

User Experience (UX) Reflections - David Green

- **CEH's UX Role:** Insights from the new UX role at the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH) were shared, focusing on the integration of user feedback in the design and development process.
- **DataLabs is being improved.** UKCEH is gathering feedback from users through surveys, interviews, and workshops to enhance its collaborative virtual research environment, DataLabs. A NERC-funded report on data discoverability will also inform these improvements.

- **Heuristics evaluation:** UKCEH is testing the usability of its products, including DataLabs, EIDC, Catalogues, and FDRI WP2. They're using a variety of experts to assess how easy these products are to use.
- **Agile Development:** Emphasis on agile development methodologies to regularly incorporate user input and improve the design process.
- **Current challenges:** Understanding users, reaching the right ones, effectively using their feedback, applying best practices to environmental data, and adapting our research methods are key challenges.

Co-Creation Toolkit Overview - Paulius Tvaranavicius

- **Introduction:** Presented the Co-Creation Toolkit for Environmental Services, which aims to provide best practices and techniques for effective co-creation.
- **Why we need such a toolkit:** a specialised UX toolkit could help address the unique challenges of creating environmental data services and products.
- **Aims of the webinar:** Gather feedback on an initial toolkit concept before further development.
- **Addressing challenges identified at the March 2024 EDS Workshop:** focus on four key themes: sharing learnings, peer engagement, time and resource efficiency, and user engagement.
- **Guided walkthrough:** Showcased how to use the toolkit to address environmental data-related challenges and involve users in the creation and development of products and services

Discussion and Feedback

- **Critical friends:** we asked if the participants would be willing to provide content for this toolkit - examples of successful co-creation, challenges faced in the field and methods used.
- **Feedback Collection:** Audience feedback was solicited to refine the toolkit and guide future work.

Next Steps

- **Toolkit Iteration:** The toolkit will be iterated based on feedback collected during the webinar.
- **Continued Engagement:** Participants were encouraged to stay involved and continue providing input to enhance the co-creation process.

Sli.do Feedback Summary

The Slido poll results from the co-creation webinar revealed the following:

- **The audience comprises diverse professionals**, with the majority identifying as data managers, data stewards, or data scientists (54%), followed by software engineers or developers (41%).
- **Over half of the participants (51%) have some prior experience with co-creation, user experience, or co-design**, while 30% have none.
- **The potential use of a co-creation toolkit is high**, with an average score of 7.5 out of 10. The toolkit would primarily be used to enhance processes, inform user-focused service design, and guide new service development.
- **The most desired content for the toolkit includes templates, co-creation methods, and checklists.**
- **A significant portion of the audience (67%) is willing to contribute to the toolkit**, either by providing content or acting as a critical friend.
- **The concept of co-creation evokes words like collaboration, cooperation, teamwork, and user-centred design.**
- **The relevance and usability of the toolkit for environmental data projects are perceived positively**, with 72% and 70% affirmative responses, respectively. However, there's uncertainty about whether any key UX topics are missing (100% "Not sure"). Possibly people did not have enough time to get familiar with the toolkit in the short amount of time.
- **Suggestions for additional features include incorporating AI, showcasing examples of bad UX or common mistakes, providing templates/examples within specific frameworks, and establishing a community discussion forum or idea-sharing platform.**
- **The webinar was considered useful**, with a 94% positive response.

The participants showed a strong interest in co-creation and a need for practical resources like the proposed toolkit. The diverse expertise of the audience and their willingness to contribute can enrich the toolkit's development. The feedback can help us create a toolkit that effectively supports co-creation in environmental data projects.

Organisers:

Jesse Alexander - Chair - Scientific Programming and Outreach Graduate at CEDA

Poppy Townsend - Speaker - WP5 lead for BOOST EDS, Community Manager at CEDA

Paulius Tvaranavicius - Speaker - Software user experience developer at BGS

Carl Watson - Speaker - Head of Analysis and Design at BGS

David Green - Speaker - Design researcher and UKCEH

Advertising text for the webinar

Subject:

EDS webinar - Putting users first: how can we co-create environmental data services that address real needs

Body:

Why attend?

One of the core aims of the [Environmental Data Service](#) is to better engage with users and ensure their needs are central to everything we do. How we design, maintain and share our services hasn't traditionally been prioritised with user feedback in mind. Many of our teams and systems are now having to change the way we work and learn new skills.

What you'll learn

In this one hour webinar, we will explore the topic of user-focussed data services. Experts within the EDS who have prior experience of designing services, with users' needs in mind, will showcase examples of best practice via a new toolkit. The toolkit includes examples and templates for techniques used for engaging users in the design process.

The webinar will end with a discussion to gather feedback from attendees about the toolkit and any additional support they need to improve how we put our users first. Some prompt questions for you to think about:

- Which templates/examples do you want to see?
- Do you have any potential content contributions?
- What barriers or challenges do you face in this area?

Save the date

Tuesday 16th July at 10-11 am (BST)

Who should join?

Anyone is welcome to attend this webinar, we think it will be of particular interest to the following types of people:

- Anyone involved with the creation of new or improved digital products and services for environmental science
- Anyone with an interest in ensuring these services are co-designed and driven by user needs
- You may be a software engineer, data scientist or steward, researcher, community engagement specialists

Why is this important?

Co-design is about ensuring data services are relevant, usable, and effective in tackling the challenges facing our society and planet. By putting users first, we will create tools and services that empower action and drive positive change.